

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Standard

Operating Procedures

Technical Documentation

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SOP overview

The overarching research goal will be to develop an efficient monitoring strategy to measure change and distinguish trends from natural variability in the EWS. With an evidence-based approach, WOBECE will address this goal by considering stakeholder knowledge and requirements and applying the best available scientific and technological knowledge. The following specific research questions (RQ) will guide the implementation of the project:

1. What is the baseline status of biodiversity and ecosystem functions within the EWS?
2. Which data and knowledge are needed to assess status, trends and mitigation measures in biodiversity changes and ecosystem services, and to identify areas of specific vulnerability and climate refugia?
3. How can the analysis of biodiversity, ecosystem functions and their relationship with environmental drivers improve future management of this changing ecosystem? Project name: Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change (WOBECE) Funding: Biodiversa+ Partners: Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) Antarctic and Southern Ocean Coalition (ASOC) Institute of Natural Sciences (INS) Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAS) Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) Stockholm University (SU) University of Rostock (UR) UiT The Arctic University of Norway (UIT) University of Groningen (UG) University of Padua (UP) Wageningen Marine Research (WMR)

1 This document

This document is an overview of the Standard Operating Practices as defined in the WOBECE project and provides links to the different documents.

The linked documents are gear-first SOPs, where the term gear is interpreted rather broadly as both equipment and people (observers). An SOP starts from the gear and describes as clearly as possible the sequential steps required for reliable and consistent results, highlighting critical points/steps and common mistakes where relevant. These documents should allow anyone with minimal level of experience and background knowledge to provide useful data.

2 General

2.1 Labeling samples

Labeling samples is essential for maintaining data integrity, ensuring traceability, and preventing errors in scientific research and environmental monitoring. Proper labeling allows researchers to accurately associate samples with their collection details, such as date, location, and methodology, which is crucial for reproducibility and meaningful analysis. It also helps in organizing and managing samples throughout processing, storage, and analysis, reducing the risk of mix-ups or contamination. Unclear labeling renders deployments useless.

3 Gear

3.1 Seafloor

3.1.1 Agassiz Trawl

The Agassiz Trawl is a benthic sampling gear designed to catch large seafloor organisms (megabenthos) such as crustaceans, echinoderms, mollusks, and demersal fishes. It features a horizontal beam with side runners and a net, constructed symmetrically to operate on either side, making it suitable for deep-sea deployments.

3.2 Water column

3.2.1 Autonomous Sampling

short-term sediment trap, Water column, Autonomous Sampling

A sediment trap is an oceanographic instrument designed to capture particles sinking through the water column, such as organic debris, plankton remnants, and mineral matter. Typically deployed at fixed depths from research vessels or moorings, the trap uses funnel-shaped collectors to channel falling material into sampling containers. The collected samples allow quantitative and qualitative analysis of vertical particle fluxes, particle composition and associated microbiomes, and biogeochemical processes.

Remote Access Sampler (RAS)

The RAS automatically collects seawater samples in defined, programmed sample intervals. Together with sensors deployed in parallel, this allows semi-quantitative analysis of pelagic microbiome dynamics in the oceanographic context.

AUTOFIM

The autonomous underway filtration system automatically pump seawater from the ship's intake and capture microbes on polycarbonate filters.

3.2.2 Echosounder

Echosounders are sonar instruments designed to detect and study aquatic organisms by transmitting acoustic signals into the water column and receiving the echoes that bounce back from targets. They are widely used in marine research to map biomass distribution, monitor fish populations, and characterize the water column. Modern scientific echosounders, such as the Simrad EK80, can operate at multiple frequencies, allowing simultaneous observation of organisms of different sizes and types, and providing detailed information on vertical and horizontal distribution patterns.

3.2.3 Plankton nets Multinet/WP2

Plankton nets are sampling tools used to collect meso- and macrozooplankton from the water column. Mesozooplankton are commonly obtained with fine-mesh nets, such as the HydroBios Multinet or WP2 ring net, which can be deployed vertically or in multiple compartments to sample at specific depths. Macrozooplankton, including krill, amphipods, and shrimps, are collected using larger trawls, such as rectangular midwater trawls or Under Ice trawls. Deployment from research vessels is carried out using cranes, winches, or trawling systems, enabling controlled sampling while maintaining the integrity of the specimens for both quantitative and qualitative analyses.

3.2.4 RMT

The Rectangular Midwater Trawl (RMT) is a net system used to sample plankton and macrozooplankton in the open water column. Its rectangular frame keeps the net mouth open during towing, enabling accurate and quantitative collection of midwater organisms such as krill, copepods, and small fish. RMTs can be towed at controlled depths and speeds from research vessels, producing reproducible samples for studies of biomass, population structure, and ecological dynamics.

3.2.5 SUIT Trawl/CTD/ADCP/GoPro/RAMSES

The Surface and Under Ice Trawl (SUIT) is a specialized trawl for sampling macrozooplankton in polar regions beneath sea ice. Mounted on a rigid frame, it can be deployed under ice to capture organisms such as krill, amphipods, and other macrofauna. The SUIT enables controlled towing while preserving sample integrity, supporting quantitative and qualitative analyses of biomass and community composition.

3.2.6 CTD rosette/sensor

A CTD is an oceanographic instrument that measures the conductivity (to derive salinity), temperature, and pressure (depth) of seawater as it is lowered through the water column. Mounted on a rosette frame that often carries water sampling bottles, the CTD provides high-resolution vertical profiles of key physical properties of the ocean. These data are essential

for understanding water mass structure, mixing processes, and overall oceanographic conditions.

3.2.7 Net Sampling

Describes the general process of sorting and preserving the catches of larger meso- and macrozooplankton sampling gear such as the Rectangular Midwater Trawl (RMT) 8+1 and de Surface and Under Ice Trawl (SUIT). The catches are used to determine the abundance and biomass of species in the meso- and macrozooplankton community, and the length-frequency distribution of krill and scallop species.

3.3 Sea ice

3.3.1 Ice Coring KOVACS/under-ice pump

A hand ice corer is a portable auger system used to extract intact cylindrical ice cores for analysis. It consists of a core barrel, cutting head, drive handle, and extension rods, and can be attached to either a hand corer or, ideally, a power drill. The KOVACS MARK II retrieves cores 9 cm in diameter and 1 m long, featuring a lightweight composite barrel, aluminium cutting shoe, and steel cutting teeth, making it efficient and reliable for field use.

3.4 UIW (Under-Ice Water)

3.4.1 Ruttner Water Sampler

A Ruttner water sampler is a straightforward, hand-operated device used to obtain discrete water samples from defined depths. The instrument consists of a cylindrical body—typically made of plastic or metal—with end caps that remain open while it is lowered through the water. It is deployed on a rope, and when it reaches the target depth, a messenger (a small weighted trigger) is released down the line to close the end caps and trap the water sample. Its durable, lightweight construction makes the Ruttner sampler particularly suitable for under-ice work and other remote field situations where simple, manually operated equipment is required.

3.4.2 SUIT

The TriOS RAMSES hyperspectral radiometer is a small, self-contained sensor used to record detailed radiance or irradiance spectra across the UV and visible wavelength ranges.

3.5 Snow

3.5.1 *Measuring stick*

3.6 Benthic

3.6.1 *MUC/BC*

Both the multi-corer (MUC) and box corer (BC) are seabed-sampling instruments, designed to collect marine sediments. While the MUC takes multiple core samples, the box corer retrieves a single, block-shaped section of the seabed.

3.7 Bird/Mammal Observations

An observer is a human individual, responsible for conducting systematic visual watches from a ship or helicopter, detecting, identifying and recording the observations according to predefined guidelines depending on the survey category.